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Data Management Plan

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AR7	Seventh Assessment Report
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CARE	Collective benefit, Authority control, Responsibility and Ethics
CC	Creative Commons
CERN	Conseil européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire
CID	Climatic Impact-Drivers
CMIP	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project
CMS	Copernicus Marine Service
CORDEX	Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
CTD	Conductivity, Temperature, and Depth
DACs	Data Archive Centres
DCC	Decade Collaborative Centre
DG DIGIT	Directorate-General for Digital Services
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
ECV	Essential Climate Variables
EDMERP	European Data Management and Exchange Platform for Research Programs
EDMO	European Directory of Marine Organisations
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
ENS	EuroGOOS Network of Systems
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOV	Essential Ocean Variables
ESA	European Space Agency
ESA CCI	ESA Climate Change Initiative rving System GRA GOOS Regional alliances
ESGF	Earth System Grid Federation
ESM	Earth System Models
EUDAT	European Data Infrastructure
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
FORCE	The Future of Research Communications and e-Scholarship
GCMD	Global Change Master Directory
GCOS	Global Climate Observing System

GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
GRA	GOOS Regional alliances
ICES	International Council for the Exploration of the Sea
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IOC	Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission
IODE	International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange
IPCC	The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
MHW	Marine heat waves
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NIRD	Norwegian Infrastructure for Research Data
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
OA	Open Access
OBPS	Ocean Best Practices System
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OPFN	Ocean Practices Federated Network
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
OSF	Open Science Framework
QC	Quality Control
RI	Research Infrastructure
ROR	Research Organization Registry
RRR	WMO Rolling Review of Requirements
SO	Specific Objective
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WCRP	World Climate Research Programme
WGS84	World Geodetic System 1984
WIGOS	WMO Integrated Global Observing System
WMO	World Meteorological Organization
WP	Work Package

Table 1: List of Abbreviations.

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1. Publishable summary

ObsSea4Clim brings together key European and international actors within ocean observing science, climate assessment, Earth System modelling, data sharing, best practices and standards, with users of oceanographic products and services. The project's goals are to enhance sustained and multipurpose observations vital to European and global climate requirements, and to deliver an improved observation framework based on Essential Ocean Variables and Essential Climate Variables (EOV/ECVs), embedded in a Rolling Review of Requirements approach.

Having a clear and structured data management plan is essential for the success of ObsSea4Clim. ObsSea4Clim has been an early adopter of the EU Open Research Repository Pilot since June 2024, and this plan ensures that data and products used and produced within the project are accurately described, follow common standards, best practices and metadata, adopt common formats, and are readily accessible to researchers, policymakers, and other project stakeholders.

This document describes the second version of the ObsSea4Clim Data Management Plan (DMP), outlining the types of data collected and used in the project work packages (WPs), presenting the planned internal data management procedures throughout the project lifecycle, and addressing data availability and stewardship after project completion.

2. About the Deliverable

The DMP is a living document and undergoes regular revisions throughout the project's duration, with subsequent versions seamlessly integrated into the first deliverable report. This document is the second version of the ObsSea4Clim Data

Management Plan - deliverable D1.3 - overseen by WP1 with contributions from all work packages.

FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable principles (Wilkinson, et al., 2016), CARE - Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics principles (Carroll, et al., 2020), and Horizon Europe's Open Research Data requirements serve as the guiding frameworks for ObsSea4Clim's data management. Following a brief overview of the ObsSea4Clim project, this document delineates the types of observational and numerical data collected and used across the project work packages, it presents the planned internal data management procedures throughout the project's lifecycle, and addresses data availability and stewardship post-project completion.

Making newly collected data available and FAIR for ObsSea4Clim stakeholders is an important project outcome. "ObsSea4Clim data" includes data either generated de novo within ObsSea4Clim or derived/linked from open, existing sources. While the reuse of pre-existing data is encouraged and essential (and in line with the European recommendation "collect once, use many times"), these data must be tagged as external/existing data.

ObsSea4Clim has become an early adopter of the EU Open Research Repository Pilot since June 2024. The [EU Open Research Repository](#) provides a space for all other research outputs, including datasets, software, posters, and presentations, that are outside the scope of Open Research Europe (ORE). This allows researchers to have a simple go-to solution for making their publicly funded research open and as FAIR as possible. This enables researchers to not only publish their findings but also share the underlying data and materials that support their work, fostering transparency and reproducibility in the scientific process. In line with this advocacy, ObsSea4Clim implements key elements to support the FAIR data and results

principles. More specifically, data are identified by Persistent identifiers (PIDs) such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) or a handle. This is applied to publications (with DOI), authors involved in the action (with ORCID), consortium organisations (with the European Directory of Marine Organizations - EDMO and/or ROR) and the grant, with the Cordis grant DOI and European Directory Marine and Environmental Research Projects.

In cases where pre-existing data collected before the start of the ObsSea4Clim project have not been previously published or deposited in an official repository, their inclusion in ObsSea4Clim can be linked to both ObsSea4Clim and the respective previous projects.

Document Disclaimers:

This document is based on the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template (V1.1, April 2022) and adapted to provide ObsSea4Clim partners and ObsSea4Clim stakeholders with a living guide for the project Data Management Plan. The European Community is not responsible for any use that may be made of the contents of this publication.

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3. Data Summary

The prompt, unrestricted and free exchange of oceanographic observational and numerical data is crucial for comprehending the oceans' intricate role in weather and climate patterns, providing decision-makers with evidence-based insights for sustainable ocean and environmental management. The European Commission and

its Member States strongly advocate for an open and free data policy to cater to the diverse environmental data service needs of user communities. Ocean observing, which encompasses the broader process and infrastructure involved in collecting data, is essential for this effort, as it provides the necessary framework for acquiring ocean observations, including the individual data points or measurements obtained through this process. The push for open data and data system interoperability has gained momentum with the establishment of FAIR principles in 2014, focusing on making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable. In 2021, the OECD introduced a Recommendation on Enhancing Access to and Sharing of Data, outlining principles and policy guidance to assist governments in maximising the cross-sectoral benefits of various data types while safeguarding individual and organisational rights. Despite these advancements, challenges persist in ensuring the availability and accessibility of ocean data and data quality characteristics (e.g. uncertainty estimate) due to non-compliance with international standards and best practices, diverse data formats, varying data management structures and the lack of sustainability of specific repositories and publication approaches (e.g. use of websites for publication). However, progress has been made in establishing fundamental milestones that can be readily adopted and tailored for specific purposes. This includes embracing open science practices throughout the entire ocean data workflow and lifecycle, encompassing data processing, validation, maintenance and dissemination infrastructure.

3.1. Aim of data collection and reuse

ObsSea4Clim is targeting several data-oriented objectives:

- to develop ocean indicators, provide improved EOV/ECVs and evolve European ocean observing;

- to develop methods, capacities, and improved skills to support multidisciplinary operational services/warnings to climate/ocean health/Green Deal;
- to improve sustained and multi-purpose observations that are critical for European and global climate needs;
- to improve the observing framework in line with European and international agreements and guidelines related to ocean observations with a focus on EOJ/ECV;
- to support studies on sea ice loss, ocean transport, stratification, sea level rise, ocean warming, ocean heat waves and ocean mesoscale phenomena;
- to advance the use of EOJ and ECVs for improved ESM and reduced uncertainty in projections (IPCC/AR7/CMIP7);
- to further the adoption of standards and best practices which support the interoperability and sustainability of ocean data and information.

In addition, ObsSea4Clim aims to establish and promote best practices to facilitate harmonisation in data quality characterisation, data FAIRness, and trustworthiness. ObsSea4Clim is organised around seven work packages, four of which deal with data processing.

Fig. 1: ObsSea4Clim interconnection of the WPs.

More specifically, WP2 to WP5 are developing new indicators and services for key oceanic phenomena and their impacts on climate. ObsSea4Clim is targeting a series of actions to facilitate and expand the availability of in situ data for use in combination with satellite data and models. Therefore, ObsSea4Clim is not collecting new in situ data per se, but its actions will make more data available within already established ocean observing systems and ocean data infrastructures.

WP2 - EOVS and ECV Framework

This work package identifies, supported by a rolling review of the requirements process (short RRR), which EOVS/ECV-oriented data should be considered for monitoring global climate information and marine extremes, ensuring alignment with the needs of European nations. It includes the refinement of best practices and standards to promote transparency, interoperability and trust in ocean information. It will develop machine-based procedures to assess uncertainties in these heterogeneous data.

WP3 - Indicator Framework

This work package works on ocean indicators (e.g., ocean warming) and marine extremes (e.g. heatwaves and sea ice extremes). It utilises data and information from various sources, including in situ ocean data reanalyses and satellite-derived products. Results would drive recommendations for the ocean observation system, including the identification of data gaps

WP4 - Application Areas for Climate EOVS/ECVs

This work package aims to enhance the understanding of key oceanic phenomena and their impacts on climate, focusing on sea-ice loss, ocean transport, ocean stratification, sea level, marine heatwaves, and ocean mesoscale dynamics. It involves validating needs, uncertainties, and approaches for capturing sea ice loss,

evaluating observing requirements for ocean transport estimates, assessing requirements for understanding ocean stratification, reviewing observing needs for monitoring sea level variability, assessing MHW detection and description, and synthesising observing requirements for ocean mesoscale dynamics. This work package uses various data sources, including satellite-derived altimetry data, satellite-derived sea surface temperature and salinity data, satellite-derived ocean colour data, and in situ measurements from buoy networks and research vessels.

WP5 - EOVs and ECVs in Support of Climate Modelling

This work package assesses the performance of state-of-the-art Earth System Models (ESMs) in reproducing key phenomena and processes identified in WP4. It will investigate the performance of ESMs at high-spatial and temporal resolution for relevant EOVs, and the capabilities of ESMs to represent extreme events at regional scales. It will support the tuning of some ESMs for CMIP7.

WP6 and WP7: These work packages do not generate research data.

3.2. Data inventory

For each work package of the project, the following information is collected:

- *Task.* A specific task in the referring WP.
- *Parameter/EOV/ECV.* Name specific to the type of data being referenced.
- *Dataset/model name.* Specific name of the model or dataset
- *Type of data.* Refer to the type of data provided, such as model or in situ data.
- *Link to source.* Reference dataset access links.
- *Short description of the data.* A concise description of the data, including information such as model version, spatial and temporal resolution, and other relevant information (e.g. *pre-existing*) .
- *Licence.* Type of licence associated with the data (CC-BY, CC0, etc.)

- *Citation and best practices.* Refers to the specific DOI or link to the methodology document describing the relevant standards and best practices used in the collection, processing, and data management.
- *Quality assurance.* Information on the characterisation, including e.g., uncertainty attributes, and assurance of data quality. This information is not yet available in this version. However, a dedicated effort is planned to collect and document quality-related aspects, such as validation approaches, uncertainty estimates and quality control procedures. These will be integrated in future updates.

This inventory is updated during the project and serves as a track for data “dimension” within the ObsSea4Clim project.

The second version of the Data Inventory snapshot, taken at the time of writing, is attached in *Annex 1*.

3.3. Data type and formats

As anticipated, the ObsSea4Clim project is divided into different WPs and Table 2 below delineates the data types consumed by each project WP, categorised into the following three main groups:

- In situ observational data.
- Earth observation products derived from satellites.
- Numerical models.

	In situ data	Earth Observation	Numerical models
WP1	-	-	-
WP2	X	X	-

	In situ data	Earth Observation	Numerical models
WP3	X	X	X
WP4	X	X	X
WP5	X	X	X
WP6	-	-	-
WP7	-	-	-

Table 2: Data types used by each WP.

3.4. Data utility outside the project

The objectives of ObsSea4Clim require clear scientific and logistical cooperation with various national and international research organisations and innovation efforts, which form the backbone of its collaborative framework.

One of the cornerstones of this collaboration is the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS), which continuously evaluates and advises on global climate observations. Through close links with GCOS, ObsSea4Clim benefits from access to key guidance and resources to improve regional and national climate observing activities. This collaboration extends to national GCOS groups and influencers such as ENS, ensuring that ObsSea4Clim remains aligned with global climate observing strategies and standards.

The project's engagement with the Global Ocean Observing System, led by UNESCO's Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC), is another important channel for international collaboration. By participating in GOOS initiatives and leveraging regional alliances such as EuroGOOS, ObsSea4Clim contributes to the development of

essential ocean observing frameworks and fosters collaboration in ocean monitoring and assessment.

ObsSea4Clim's partnership with the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO) further enhances its climate reporting and observing capabilities. Specifically, the project focuses on global climate indicators such as ocean warming, sea surface temperature, as well as extremes such as marine heatwaves, in line with the WMO's mandate on weather, climate, and water-related issues. By collaborating with organisations such as the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), the Copernicus Marine Service (CMS) and EMODnet, ObsSea4Clim will gain access to critical datasets and analytical tools, enriching its capacity for climate analysis and prediction. ObsSea4Clim utilises data from EMODnet to monitor and understand ocean phenomena essential for climate analysis and prediction. In particular, EMODnet will play a key role in implementing the RRR strategy for ocean climate observing. Operational workflows will be established to ensure the provision of Essential Ocean Variables and Essential Climate Variables as a new data service for EMODnet. In addition to global initiatives, ObsSea4Clim develops relevant solutions (e.g. indicators) in support of the UNFCCC Ocean and Climate Change Dialogue and the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development. These engagements underline ObsSea4Clim's commitment to advancing ocean science and sustainability goals on a global scale. By collaborating with partners across different projects and programmes, ObsSea4Clim amplifies its impact and contributes to the collective effort towards a more sustainable future.

In the European context, ObsSea4Clim builds upon the outcomes of projects such as [AtlantOS](#) and [EuroSea](#), utilising their insights and frameworks to enhance European ocean observing systems and sustainability efforts. Furthermore, by clustering with other projects funded under the same call, ObsSea4Clim aims to foster synergies,

reduce duplication and maximise the impact of collective efforts to advance ocean observation, research and policy.

4. FAIR Data Principles

The objectives and benefits of the ObsSea4Clim project are intrinsically linked to achieving long-term outcomes. The efforts contribute to the improvement of Earth System Models (ESMs), such as CMIP7, and the refinement of extreme event statistics in climate projections through the intercomparison of different records and a rigorous assessment of limitations and caveats. The aim is to provide better climate information. This work also advances the understanding of key physical ocean processes related to climate change by evaluating historical simulations and global projections, with a focus on the mechanisms driving sea ice loss, sea level rise, changes in ocean heat content, and extreme events. By leveraging international initiatives and collaborating with relevant projects, the aim is to refine climate projections and deepen our understanding of abrupt changes or tipping points in the climate system. These contributions are crucial to the advancement of climate science and the development of more accurate and robust climate projections, which are supported by the efforts of ObsSea4Clim.

In this context, it is essential to adhere to the FAIR Guiding Principles, formulated by Wilkinson et al. in 2016, which provide a robust framework for enhancing the reusability of scientific data, with a particular emphasis on machine actionability. These principles, encompassing **Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability**, operate at both metadata and data levels. Findability entails assigning globally unique and persistent identifiers to data, accompanied by comprehensive metadata descriptions that include origin, context, and usage information.

Additionally, metadata should explicitly link to the associated data, and both should be registered or indexed in searchable resources such as data repositories.

Since 1960, the International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange (IODE) has played a pivotal role in advancing standards for data harmonisation, quality assessment, and control. The IODE has been publishing manuals and guides that cover operational procedures for data collection, quality assessment, quality control, standards, reference materials, data formats, and more. Harmonisation of marine in situ data is necessary for scientists from different disciplines and experts in various fields to share information and collaboratively address specific marine phenomena or threats. The marine data landscape is diverse and complex, with repositories known as data archive centres (DACs) providing access to raw data, metadata, and data products.

European programmes and projects such as Copernicus, EMODnet, SeaDataNet, and H2020 EuroSea have significantly contributed to advancing FAIR principles by aligning with the 15 characteristics laid down by the FORCE11¹ collective. Studies by Tanhua et al. (2019) and Quimbert et al. (2022) have detailed these advancements, highlighting significant progress in data standards and machine-to-machine data processing over the past three decades. These initiatives adhere to FAIR principles, providing a comprehensive framework for effective data management.

¹ <https://force11.org/info/the-fair-data-principles/> FORCE11 is a community of scholars, librarians, archivists, publishers and research funders that has arisen organically to help facilitate the change toward improved knowledge creation and sharing.

Findable	
F1	(meta)data are assigned a globally unique and eternally persistent identifier.
F2	data are described with rich metadata.
F3	(meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.
F4	metadata specifies the data identifier.
Accessible	
A1	(meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol.
A1.1	the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable.
A1.2	the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary.
A2	metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available.
Interoperable	
I1	(meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
I2	(meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.
I3	(meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.
Re-usable	
R1	(meta)data have a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.
R1.1	(meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage licence.
R1.2	(meta)data are associated with their provenance.
R1.3	(meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards.

Table 3: FAIR principles introduced by the [FORCE11](#) community.

The recommendations consistently incorporate three key components to ensure interoperability: metadata encompassing data quality, data format, and data services.

Specifically, the **metadata** for published works must adhere to a **Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0)** or an equivalent, aligning with FAIR principles, particularly emphasising machine-actionability. This metadata should include essential details such as author(s), title, publication date, venue, Horizon Europe or other funding information, grant project specifics, licensing terms, and persistent identifiers for publications, authors, organisations, and grants. Additionally, where applicable, persistent identifiers for research outputs and necessary tools for validating publication conclusions should be included. In addition, metadata should consist of the (link to the) methods used to create and process the data to ensure complete documentation and reproducibility.

In terms of data availability, partners are required to make their research data available promptly and within the timeframes specified in the DMP, thus ensuring open access (also in accordance with the EU Open Research Repository Pilot requirements).

However, the usability of **data** is strongly influenced by the data licence. There is a growing trend to adopt the CC-BY license, which allows unrestricted use, subject only to proper attribution to the creator. Where necessary, data embargoes and other CC licences may be used, following the principle of 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary'.

Partners may deviate from providing Open Access in two circumstances: where Open Access conflicts with the legitimate interests of the beneficiary, particularly in relation to commercial exploitation; or where it conflicts with other constraints, such as EU competitive interests or obligations under the Agreement. This is not expected with ObsSea4Clim.

Any decision to withhold open access to data, in whole or in part, has to be reported and justified by partners in the data management plan (more specifically under Annex 1 - Data Inventory).

4.1. Making data Findable

ObsSea4Clim utilises a combination of in situ ocean observations, satellite-derived data, and model outcomes and products to develop new EOV/ECV-based indicators and to update and enhance ESMs, thereby improving the capability to understand climate change and extreme events. Making these outcomes findable means developing a catalogue that serves both human and computer interactions. ObsSea4Clim has adopted Zenodo as a tool to manage the project's outcomes catalogue. A specific community² was set up to provide stakeholders with an easy catalogue to search, to manage persistent digital identifiers (DOI) for each project digital outcome and to have a standardized tool for describing and linking actors (researchers, institutions and funding agencies), best practice and outcomes (URL to the dataset, product or service).

4.2. Making data Accessible

Accessibility emphasises retrievability via standardised protocols that are open, free and universally implementable while ensuring data security through authentication and authorisation procedures. In ObsSea4Clim, all contributions are CC BY 4.0 "unrestricted" standard, by default.

All digital outcomes are listed in the ObsSea4Clim Zenodo community, and each data-product item in the catalogue provides the user with a link (URL) to access the data-product. Whenever possible, data products are available through trusted data

² <https://zenodo.org/communities/obssea4clim/records?q=&|list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

repositories, such as EUDAT, ESGF, NIRD (for Norwegian institutions), or EU Marine Data Initiatives. Whenever possible, relevant method descriptions and documents should be available through the Ocean Best Practices System (OBPS).

4.3. Making data Interoperable

Interoperability depends on the use of a formal, accessible, and standardised language for knowledge representation in metadata, accompanied by vocabularies that adhere to FAIR principles and include both qualified references to other datasets and the methods used to create and manage them, thus facilitating comprehensive analysis.

The use of controlled vocabularies ensures consistent application of terminology, thereby supporting the universality and seamless integration of metadata across different systems. This is essential for interoperability, as it facilitates the accurate and efficient discovery, evaluation and use of data across a wide range of applications.

Data interoperability also stems from the use of documented methods for preparing, collecting, and processing data, utilising best practices (Mantovani et al., 2024). These practices should be identified and linked to data sets so that regional and global observations can be more effectively intercompared.

4.4. Making data Reusable

Reusability focuses on enriching metadata with accurate attributes, providing clear data usage licences, documenting detailed provenance, and ensuring adherence to domain-relevant community standards and practices. In ObsSea4Clim, ESM experiment protocols and results are made available as peer-reviewed publications or online via the Zenodo repository. Moreover, the project supports open science principles and, besides adopting open gold access for publications, it is committed

to publishing any research output and tools, also codes and cookbooks, by platforms like GitHub³ (in combination with Zenodo to ensure full project outcomes FAIRness).

4.5. Minimum Set of Metadata

Metadata serves as critical information that provides context and organisation to various data formats. It includes essential details such as source, creation date, authorship, physical access protocols, semantics of the data and more.

It is equally crucial to clarify the vocabulary and standards used. The use of controlled vocabularies ensures consistency in the use of terminology, making metadata universally understandable and seamlessly integrable across disparate systems. Such standardisation is critical to promoting interoperability and streamlining the accurate and efficient discovery, evaluation and use of data across applications.

A minimum set of metadata has been defined to ensure comprehensive identification of the spatial, temporal, depth, source, and quality control aspects for each dataset/product. This metadata framework includes essential standards to ensure consistency and interoperability. For the spatial dimension, the WGS84 standard must be used to ensure accurate geographic positioning. For the temporal dimension, the ISO 8601 standard must be used, which provides a clear and consistent format for representing dates and times. The vocabulary used in keywords should be consistent with the GCMD to ensure consistency and facilitate data discovery.

Detailed specifications of the minimum metadata required and the applicable standards are provided in Annex 2, where a comprehensive table outlines each element and the corresponding standards to be applied, where available.

³ ObsSea4Clim GitHub repository is available at <https://github.com/ObsSea4clim>.

5. Open Science

Open Science is a global approach that aims to make all aspects of the research process as transparent, accessible, and reusable as possible, enabling more collaborative, inclusive, and impactful science. It supports the entire research lifecycle by promoting transparency and accessibility throughout the project design, data collection, analysis, and dissemination phases. According to the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (2021)⁴, its objectives include fostering scientific collaboration, improving reproducibility, and ensuring that scientific knowledge benefits both science and society.

Key components of Open Science include the development and use of digital infrastructures that support data sharing, long-term preservation, and discoverability of research outputs. These infrastructures range from domain-specific and generalist repositories to collaborative platforms like the Open Science Framework (OSF), which enables versioned project management, documentation, and data sharing across teams. Open Science also relies on Open Access publishing practices, ensuring that articles, datasets, software, and protocols are freely available and not restricted by subscription fees, thereby increasing their visibility, reuse, and citation potential (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Open Science Blocks.

⁴ <https://en.unesco.org/science-sustainable-future/open-science/recommendation>

The European Commission's main platform for supporting the OSF is CORDIS⁵ (Community Research and Development Information Service), which lists all the EU-funded research projects. CORDIS provides access to digital outputs from projects and interoperates with the OpenAIRE system, a key implementer of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). OpenAIRE promotes open scholarship and improves discoverability, accessibility, shareability, reusability, reproducibility, and monitoring of data-driven research results globally.

Having the project's outcome correctly listed and published in CORDIS means supporting the EU recommendations for Open Science. Having the project's outcome correctly listed and published in CORDIS requires that all the project's digital outcomes are correctly linked to the project's grant agreement number and made available under an OpenAIRE system.

With its Zenodo community and the recommendation on Data Management, ObsSea4Clim is in line with the EU requirements for Open Science.

Moreover, ObsSea4Clim promotes the use of tools such as the F-UJI FAIR⁶ that perform automated assessments of how well a dataset complies with the FAIR principles. By simply entering a dataset's DOI or URL, researchers receive a detailed report with indicators and a numerical score that reflect the dataset's FAIRness level. The assessment covers areas such as the completeness of metadata, licensing, use of standards and persistent identifiers, and availability of provenance. The results help improve ObsSea4Clim data management practices and FAIR compliance throughout the project lifecycle.

⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101136548>

⁶ <https://www.f-ujl.net/> - developed under the FAIRsFAIR initiative, F-UJI is an open-source, online service that performs automated assessments of how well a dataset complies to the FAIR principles

5.1. Open Access

Open Access is a fundamental principle of Open Science, providing free and unrestricted access to research results in order to promote transparency, collaboration and the sharing of knowledge.

ObsSea4Clim is committed to Open Access and is an early adopter of the EU Open Research Repository Pilot. This special status allows ObsSea4Clim to establish a curated repository within Zenodo in support of the EU Open Science policy. The ObsSea4Clim Zenodo community functions as a thematic repository, helping to organise and make visible the project's research outputs and materials. It enables the broad sharing of presentations, posters, meeting proceedings, and public deliverables (after approval by the European Commission reviewers), beyond the peer-reviewed articles covered by Open Research Europe (ORE).

Each document uploaded to Zenodo is assigned a unique DOI unless it already has one. If a document has already been assigned a DOI, this can be retained and registered in Zenodo. This ensures that all materials, including reports and presentations, can be found and cited through a persistent and reliable link. Zenodo assigns two types of DOIs: one that always points to the latest version of a record, and one that refers to the specific version being cited. As already mentioned, by appropriately setting the project's contract number and utilising the ORCID⁷ for authors/researchers, this platform supports full project legacy and facilitates the reporting process to the EC. More information on how to use Zenodo can be found in the Annex 3.

⁷ <https://orcid.org/> - ORCID is a free, unique, and persistent identifier that researchers can use to consistently link their work across research, scholarship, and innovation activities.

5.1.1. Open Access to Scientific Publications

Beneficiaries are required to ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications related to their results. Specifically, they must:

- Deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a trusted repository at the latest by the time of publication.
- Provide immediate open access to the deposited publication via the repository under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or an equivalent license.
- Include information in the repository about any research output or tools needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.
- Retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements.
- Ensure that the metadata of deposited publications are open under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or an equivalent license, in line with the FAIR principles, and include specific information such as publication details, funding information, licensing terms, and persistent identifiers.

Only publication fees in fully open-access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications are eligible for reimbursement.

Further details on how to comply with the Open Access requirements of this project can be found in the Project Handbook (D1.1).

5.2. Research Data Outcomes

In line with Open Access principles, the ObsSea4Clim project is committed to ensuring that its research data outputs are readily accessible and usable by the

wider scientific community and stakeholders. A key effort is to continuously update the catalogue (see Annex 1 - Data Inventory Snapshot), incorporating the latest updates from the project activities. Additionally, as planned in WP2, a feedback loop with data sources will be established to enhance data availability and quality. All products and services generated by ObsSea4Clim are made openly available in FAIR and TRUST repositories, and both the DMP and its Data Inventory Annex keep track of what has been produced, used and where and how this is stored. This approach not only facilitates the dissemination of knowledge but also promotes transparency and reproducibility in oceanographic research.

5.2.1. In Situ Data

In the ObsSea4Clim project, all in-situ data originate from established workflows and networks that have evolved from advancements made by the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) community, particularly the European component (EuroGOOS), in developing operational physical oceanography capabilities. Starting from these networks, the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) has been identified as the European hub for in-situ data. EMODnet Physics, one of the seven thematic projects implementing the program, aligns with the principle to “collect once and use many times” and builds on existing infrastructures. EMODnet Physics is federated with other main European data aggregating infrastructures, namely, the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service - In Situ Thematic Assembly Centre for operational data flow, SeaDataNet and its network of National Oceanographic Data Centres for research-quality delayed mode data, the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea, the Joint Technical Commission for Oceanography and Marine Meteorology In-Situ Observations Programme Support Centre (OceanOPS), as well as other specialised databases/infrastructures that align with EMODnet [Physics] goals. This integration ensures that in-situ data is consolidated, offering a single point of access to in-situ ocean physics time-series data, vertical profiles, data products, and metadata built with common standards, free of charge and without restrictions. More specifically, time series and datasets are made available as recorded by fixed platforms (moorings, tide gauges, HF radars, etc.), moving platforms (ARGO, Lagrangian buoys, ferryboxes, etc.), and repeated observations (CTDs, etc.). ObsSea4Clim is consuming data from these infrastructures and, by consuming data, is implementing gap analysis that will help discover and include more data into these European data aggregators.

The assessment of metadata completeness and quality, combined with the utilisation of resources like the OBPS open repository and support from organisations such as IEEE, will foster alignment with international standards and best practices.

Moreover, these initiatives are usually parameter-oriented. For example, in EMODnet Physics or the Copernicus Marine Service In Situ Thematic Assembly Center, the available themes cover temperature, salinity and current profiles, sea level trends, wave height and period, wind speed and direction, water turbidity (light attenuation), underwater noise, and river flow. The shift towards an EOVs/ECVs-centric system will support and enable the widening of the scope and stakeholders of these European data infrastructures.

The amount of new in situ data available in European marine in situ data integrators (e.g. EMODnet Physics) and the amount of updated metadata quality attached to this data will be used as KPIs for the ObsSea4Clim, enabling and facilitating actions on in situ data.

5.2.2. Models

ObsSea4Clim will advance key physical ocean processes related to climate and time change by evaluating the performance of historical simulations and global and regional projections of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project version 5 and 6 (CMIP5 and CMIP6), the Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX) as well as recent high resolution global climate model outputs from Destination Earth initiative and data from Multi-Model Large Ensemble Archive (MMLEA). The project will support the development and improvement of Earth System Models (ESMs) for the next generation (CMIP7) by enhancing parameterisation and fine-tuning model parameters to minimise bias in specific regions.

Since its inception, the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) has prioritised making its data accessible to the wider scientific community. This accessibility requires extensive collaboration to address challenges related to hardware and software, including storage, searchability, and retrieval of large datasets. To facilitate this, CMIP data are hosted on the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF). This international collaboration underpins most global climate change research, including assessments by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). ESGF manages the first distributed database of climate science data, spanning several petabytes across dozens of federated sites worldwide, and supports CMIP and CORDEX, which are essential to the periodic assessments of the IPCC.

Researchers are encouraged to follow the CMIP documentation, which provides comprehensive guidance on data access, analysis, and collaboration (<https://pcmdi.llnl.gov/CMIP6/>).

Following these recommendations ensures consistency and interoperability within the climate modelling community. Additionally, researchers must comply with the CMIP6 data citation guidelines (<http://bit.ly/2gBCuqM>). It is also important to refer to the repository (https://github.com/WCRP-CMIP/CMIP6_CVs) that collects all the metadata of the CMIP6 models and experiments, including the characterisation of state variables (description, units, output frequency, etc.). These controlled vocabularies (CVs) serve as the basic information for standardising the format of output data published on ESGF.

5.2.2.1. Long-term Simulations

For the ObsSea4Clim project, long-term preservation is facilitated by utilising the project's simulation data in the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF), which guarantees data preservation for 10 years from the date of publication. The ESGF is an

international collaboration focused on developing and maintaining software infrastructure for managing, disseminating, and analysing climate science data. It aims to advance Earth system science by providing global access to an extensive distributed database of model outputs. CMIP6 simulations are already available, and CMIP7 simulations will be stored in the ESGF's distributed database, facilitating wide accessibility and collaboration within the scientific community.

5.2.2.2. EDITO and EDITO Data Lab

EDITO (European Digital Twin Ocean) is an EU initiative aimed at developing a high-resolution, data-driven digital replica of the ocean. By integrating data from satellite observations, in situ measurements, and ocean models, it supports scientific research, policy-making, and innovation. EDITO promotes Open Science by providing a platform that adheres to the FAIR principles, facilitating the sharing, visualisation, and reuse of ocean data and simulations.

One component of this infrastructure is the EDITO Model Lab, a cloud-based, collaborative environment where researchers can upload, configure, and run marine simulations. The Model Lab supports comparative analysis across models, encourages the joint design of experiments and ensures the full traceability of results.

The EDITO Model Lab is designed to integrate models and model outputs that support the European research landscape that is implementing the *EU Mission: Restore Our Ocean and Waters*

The EDITO Model Lab is a target initiative to host some of the ObsSea4Clim outcomes.

5.2.3. Ocean Indicators

The ObsSea4Clim project is developing new strategies through multidisciplinary collaboration to improve the transfer of ocean knowledge, with a particular focus on ocean indicators. These indicators, crucial at the interface between science and policy,

have traditionally suffered from a lack of innovative dissemination tools. Given the multiple environmental stressors affecting the ocean, such as Climatic Impact Drivers (CIDs; IPCC, 2022), including ocean warming, salinity changes, and stratification, it is imperative to develop a comprehensive understanding of these factors. This project will analyse these CIDs in the North Atlantic and European regional seas to reveal the combined effects of long-term changes. By developing new tools to monitor these changes, the project will support evidence-based decision-making and policy formulation. It will develop new products to be included under the Copernicus Marine Service - Ocean Monitoring Indicators (<https://marine.copernicus.eu/access-data/ocean-monitoring-indicators>).

5.2.4.Ocean Best Practices

ObsSea4clim also leverages its efforts to address and further the use of Ocean Best Practices. The Ocean Best Practices System (OBPS) is a global initiative aimed at improving and standardising ocean data collection, analysis, and sharing. It features a searchable database, peer-reviewed research, tutorials, and guides, and organises annual events to advance ocean science. OBPS promotes best practices to enhance data quality, interoperability, and collaboration, contributing to sustainable ocean management. However, it faces challenges such as transparency, cultural barriers, and limited incentives for adopting standardised methods.

Best Practices and standards used in building and running the models and ocean indicators should be identified. Best practices should be submitted to the IOC Ocean Best Practices System (www.oceanbestpractices.org).

ObsSea4Clim is contributing to the development of the Ocean Practices Federated Network (OPFN), which is a global, distributed network of community-driven repositories. OPFN connects infrastructures such as OBPS, FAO and ICES, providing unified access to a variety of methodological collections. By applying FAIR and CARE

principles, OPFN fosters cross-disciplinary collaboration, shared governance, and the development of high-quality, searchable best practices (more in [Milestone 17](#) - *Preliminary Design of a Federated Network for Methodologies in Ocean Observing*).

6. Impact

6.1. Policy relevance

The ObsSea4Clim DMP proposes a refined scheme for data provision and evaluation by the Commission within the Horizon Europe project, with a focus on improving data FAIRness. In particular, it advocates for the widespread adoption of Creative Commons licences, particularly CC-BY, wherever feasible. In addition, the plan proposes clear guidelines for handling embargoed data, allowing for scientific processing and refinement, while ensuring eventual accessibility and linkage. ObsSea4Clim is committed to making all data openly available and easily traceable (with quality provenance) throughout the project's life cycle. Collaboration with major European marine data integrators such as EMODnet, Copernicus Marine Service and EDITO, is prioritised to maximise the utility of the project data. While not all ObsSea4Clim data can be integrated into these platforms due to their size or type, efforts will be made to facilitate seamless connections aimed at supporting interoperability where possible.

Understanding the relevance of ObsSea4Clim results in terms of CMIP and extreme events is crucial for addressing the multiple dimensions of climate impacts on the ocean. ObsSea4Clim addresses two interrelated aspects: long-term changes and extreme events triggered by these changes within the climate system. Long-term changes gradually reshape the mean state of the ocean, influencing the occurrence, duration, and intensity of extreme events. For example, global warming intensifies and increases the frequency of tropical cyclones, leading to pronounced sea level

variations in coastal regions. Consequently, ocean observations related to climate include both long-term records and operational services, including assessments of ocean health. The use of these multi-purpose ocean observations for climate studies requires interoperability, ensuring adherence to best practices and standards, and availability in line with the FAIR data concept.

7. Allocation of Resources

7.1. Costs before making data or other research outputs FAIR

Costs incurred before making data or other research outputs FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) include expenses related to data cleaning, metadata creation, standardisation, and the implementation of interoperability with identified repositories (e.g., EMODnet, Copernicus Marine Service). These costs are allocated by the project to the project partners as part of their activities and tasks within the workplace.

7.2. Responsible for data management

Data management is included in a dedicated project work package (WPI) and is led by Antonio Novellino, who has extensive experience in data management, particularly in marine data management and sharing. Antonio holds a PhD in Biotechnology and Bioengineering, an MSc in Biomedical Engineering, and is a certified Data Scientist. His expertise encompasses best practices in operational oceanographic data management and standards, FAIRness of ocean data, and downstream applications of marine data. He is one of the EMODnet coordinators, and a member of key ocean data management steering/technical working groups in international initiatives (EMODnet, Copernicus Marine Service, EuroGOOS TTs, OceanPrediction DCC, etc) and Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe marine projects .

7.3. Long-term Preservation

As previously mentioned, ObsSea4Clim implements several procedures to ensure the long-term preservation of project results and data (refer to Chapter 5).

Whenever a community-trusted repository for a new digital object is not available, ObsSea4Clim will store it in the Zenodo community.

Additionally, the Data Management Plan (DMP) and its *Annex 1 - Data Inventory* provide a continuous up-to-date version of the project datasets. This includes full links to locate, access, interoperate with, and reuse any project outcomes.

8. Data security

Data security refers to the practice of protecting digital information from unauthorised access, corruption, or theft throughout its entire lifecycle.

ObsSea4Clim is working with already available public data products and encourages data FAIRness and open data access; therefore, a discussion on data security policy is not relevant.

Nevertheless, the ObsSea4Clim DMP recommends applying good data security practices to partners that are hosting services or products used to implement the project's goals.

9. Ethical aspects

This document focuses on the management of observational data collected, which is not ethically relevant.

For information on ethical aspects, please refer to the specific deliverables D7.1- Ethics Requirements and its update, the deliverable D7.2 - *OEI - Requirement No. 2, A report by the Ethics Advisor*.

9.1. Surveys and questionnaires

Before conducting any surveys, interviews or questionnaires involving human participants, or any other activity involving the collection of opinions or data from individuals or institutions, it is essential to ensure full compliance with the project's ethical requirements.

Before launching any survey, the following aspects must be clearly defined:

- Target audience: who will be addressed?
- Survey type and content: the format and objectives of the planned activity;
- Additional data collection: whether further surveys or interviews will be conducted.
- Respondents' role: whether participants are responding in a personal capacity or on behalf of an organisation with a formal mandate.

All surveys must be created using the EU Survey platform: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/home/welcome>.

Tools such as Microsoft Forms or Google Forms are not permitted.

EU Survey is the European Commission's official tool for managing surveys. It supports a broad range of question types, from simple multiple choice and text fields

to complex elements such as editable tables and multimedia integration. Hosted by the Commission's Directorate-General for Digital Services (DG DIGIT), the platform is free for all EU citizens to use and ensures that all collected data is stored securely on European servers.

For detailed guidance on creating surveys, refer to the official [EU Survey Quick Start Guide \(PDF\)](#).

10. Updates of the DMP

The current version of ObsSea4Clim DMP will be updated for a last version in month 42, with Deliverable 1.6 Data Management Plan v. 3.

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CMIP6 - Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6
<https://pcmdi.llnl.gov/CMIP6/>

CORDEX - Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment
<https://cordex.org/>

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https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf

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<https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/for-authors/data-guidelines>

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11. Contribution to the ObsSea4Clim objectives

Organised and interoperable data that is easily accessible is a key element of the ObsSea4Clim foundation. ObsSea4Clim DMP establishes the frameworks and guidelines for managing and sharing project data. This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific objectives of the project.

SO3	<p>To create an interoperable data ecosystem serving multidisciplinary needs</p>
<p>ObsSea4Clim aims to create an interoperable data ecosystem for ocean observations, moving from parameter-centric to EOV/ECV-centric approaches. Its data management plan ensures seamless data exchange across regional and global scales, and facilitates multidisciplinary use in particular. By establishing protocols for collection, storage and sharing, it enhances transparency and supports the European Green Deal agenda. In addition, it supports the development of innovative solutions and optimised parameterisation of Earth System Models, as outlined in the project objectives.</p>	
SO4	<p>To develop best practices and standards for interoperable in-situ and satellite observing</p>
<p>The DMP serves as the framework for data interoperability, a central aspect of ObsSea4Clim's scientific strategy. This interoperability, endorsed by international bodies, enhances the EOV/ECV framework and enables cooperation in regional and global applications. Measurable outcomes include the development of quality standards and best practices, and the assessment of observing capabilities against climate requirements. In addition, proposed advances in quality control and validation methods, such as AI and neural networks, will improve data</p>	

transformation into interoperable EOV/ECVs, benefiting both current and future observations.

Annex 1: Data Inventory Snapshot

Table 4 contains the data used and produced by the partners of ObsSea4Clim. The Data Inventory file for DMP v.2., is continuously reviewed by partners and is updated in each version of the DMP.

WPI								
N	Task	Parameter /EOV/ECV	Dataset/Model Name	Type of Data	Link to Source	Brief description of the data	License	Citation (DOI/link to methodology paper or Best Practice)
//	//	//	//	//	//	//	//	//

WP2								
N	Task	Parameter/ EOV/ECV	Dataset/Model Name	Type of Data	Link to Source	Brief description of the data	License	Citation (DOI/link to methodology paper or Best Practice)
1	2.4	Subsurface temperature	EMODnet Physics - Collection of sea temperature (TEMP) Profiles -MultiPointProfiles Observation	In situ	https://ercompwebapps.emodnet-physics.eu/erddap/tabledap/PR_TEMP.html	EMODnet Physics - Collection of sea temperature (TEMP) Profiles - MultiPointProfilesObservation	CC-BY-SA	Data are the property of the producer/owner distributed through EMODnet Physics. EMODnet Physics and the partners are not responsible for improper use

2	2.4	Sea surface and subsurface temperature	Density of in-situ measurements of Water Temperature from platforms available in EMODnet-Physics - Global, 1°x1°, Monthly, 1889-2024	In situ	https://erddap.s4oceandata.eu/erddap/griddap/DENSITY_TEMP.html	<p>The dataset provides monthly density maps of in situ temperature measurements aggregated into a spatial grid with a resolution of 1° x 1°. Each grid cell contains the total number of days in the month on which temperature measurements were recorded, with values ranging from 0 (no data) to the number of days in the month. The data comes from EMODnet Physics, which integrates in situ observations from different platforms. The dataset highlights the temporal availability of temperature data at different locations.</p>	CC-BY 4.0	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14712265
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3	2.4	Salinity	Density of in-situ measurements of Water Salinity from platforms available in EMODnet-Physics - Global, 1°x1°, Monthly, 1900-2024	In situ	https://erddap.s4oceandata.eu/erddap/griddap/DENSITY_PSA.html	<p>The dataset provides monthly density maps of in situ temperature measurements aggregated into a spatial grid with a resolution of 1° x 1°. Each grid cell contains the total number of days in the month on which temperature measurements were recorded, with values ranging from 0 (no data) to the number of days in the month. The data comes from EMODnet Physics, which integrates in situ observations from different platforms. The dataset highlights the temporal availability of temperature data at different locations.</p>	CC-BY 4.0	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14712265
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4	2.4	Surface currents and subsurface currents	Density of in-situ measurements of Currents from platforms available in EMODnet-Physics - Global, 1°x1°, Monthly, 2017-2024	In situ	https://erddap.s4oceandata.eu/erddap/griddap/DENSITY_EWCT_NSCT.html	<p>The dataset provides monthly density maps of in situ temperature measurements aggregated into a spatial grid with a resolution of 1° x 1°. Each grid cell contains the total number of days in the month on which temperature measurements were recorded, with values ranging from 0 (no data) to the number of days in the month. The data comes from EMODnet Physics, which integrates in situ observations from different platforms. The dataset highlights the temporal availability of temperature data at different locations.</p>	CC-BY 4.0	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14712265
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WP3								
N	Task	Parameter/EOV/ECV	Dataset/Model Name	Type of Data	Link to Source	Brief description of the data	License	Citation (DOI/link to methodology paper or Best Practice)
1	3.1	Sea ice surface temperature	Copernicus-Marine-Service	Satellite	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/SEAICE_ARC_PHY_CLIMATE_L4_MY_011_016/description	Level 4 Arctic Sea and Ice surface temperature product based upon reprocessed AVHRR, (A)ATSR and SLSTR SST observations from the ESA CCI project, the Copernicus C3S project and the AASTI dataset. The product is a daily interpolated field with a 0.05 degrees resolution, and covers surface temperatures in the ocean, the sea ice and the marginal ice zone.		https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00123

2	3.2	Temperature, ocean velocity, salinity, sea surface height	Mediterranean Sea Physics Reanalysis	Model	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/MEDSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_006_004/description	The Med MFC physical multiyear product is a reanalysis product for the mediterranean sea (1/24° horizontal resolution, 141 vertical levels) for the period 1 Jan 1987 to 1 Feb 2024.	https://doi.org/10.25423/CMCC/MEDSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_006_004_E3R1
3	3.2	Temperature, ocean velocity, salinity, sea surface height	Global Ocean Physics Reanalysis	Model	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_PHY_001_030/description	The GLORYS12V1 product is the CMEMS global ocean eddy-resolving (1/12° horizontal resolution, 50 vertical levels) reanalysis covering the altimetry (1993 onward).	https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00021
4	3.2	Sea Surface Temperature	Mediterranean Sea - High Resolution L4 Sea Surface Temperature Reprocessed	Satellite	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/SST_MED_SST_L4_REP_OBSERVATIONS_010_021/description	The Reprocessed Mediterranean dataset provides a stable and consistent long-term Sea Surface Temperature (SST) time series over the Mediterranean Sea developed for climate applications on a 0.05deg.x 0.05deg.	https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00173

						horizontal grid resolution. Period 3 Oct 1992 to 8 Jun 2023	
5	3.2	Air-sea heat flux	ERA5 hourly data on single levels	Model	https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview	ECMWF reanalysis for the global climate and weather, combining model data with observations (1940-present). Hourly data are obtained at 0.25° x 0.25° spatial resolution for the variables: surface net solar radiation, surface net thermal radiation, surface sensible heat flux and surface latent heat flux, for the period 1993-2022.	https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.adbb2d47

6	3.2; 4.5	Mean sea level pressure, 10m u component of wind, 10m v component of wind, surface latent heat flux, surface net solar radiation, surface sensible heat flux, surface sensible heat flux, surface net thermal radiation, 2m temperature, geopotential	ERA5 hourly data on single levels	Reanalysis	https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview	Fifth-generation ECMWF reanalysis for the global climate and weather, combining model data and observations. On a 0.25° x 0.25° resolution. Data is available from 1940 onwards.
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7	3.2; 4.5	Mixed layer depth, u component of current, v component of current	Global Ocean Physics Reanalysis - GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_PHY_001_030 - cmems_mod_glo_phy_my_0.083deg_P1D-m	Reanalysis	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_PHY_001_030/description	CMEMS global ocean eddy-resolving (1/12° horizontal resolution, 50 vertical levels, 1993 onwards). Daily mean values.		
8	3.2; 4.5	Sea water potential temperature	Global Ocean Physics Analysis and Forecast - GLOBAL_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_001_024 - cmems_mod_glo_phy-thetao_anfc_0.083deg_P1D-m		https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/GLOBAL_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_001_024/description	Operational Mercator global ocean analysis and forecast system at 1/12 degree is providing 10-day forecasts updated daily. Daily mean potential temperature at 0.5 m.		
9	3.2; 4.5	Sea Surface Temperature	Sea surface temperature daily data from 1979 to present, derived from satellite observations	Satellite	https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/satellite-sea-surface-temperature?tab=overview	Daily estimates of global sea surface temperature based on observations from multiple satellite sensors: AVHRRs, ATSRs and SLSTR. On a 0.05° x 0.05° resolution for Level-4 products. Level-4 provides a spatially complete		

						global dataset. Data from September 1981 to present.		
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10	3.1	Sea Surface Temperature	daily_SST_Irish_Met_Buoys	Observations	https://erddap.marine.ie/erddap/tabledap/IWBNetwork.csv?station_id%2CCallSign%2CLongitude%2Clatitude%2Ctime%2CAtmosphericPressure%2CWindDirection%2CWindSpeed%2CGust%2CWaveHeight%2CWavePeriod%2CMeanWaveDirection%2CHmax%2CAirTemperature%2CDewPoint%2CSeaTemperature%2Csalinity%2CRelativeHumidity%2CSprTp%2CThTp%2CTp%2COC_Flag&time%3E=2023-03-24T10%3A10%3A58Z	<p>The Irish Marine Data Buoy Observation Network (Weather Buoy Network) is managed by the Marine Institute in collaboration with Met Éireann and the UK Met Office. The Irish Weather Buoy Network is designed to improve weather forecasts and safety at sea around Ireland. The buoy network provides vital data for weather forecasts, shipping bulletins, gale and swell warnings as well as data for general public information and research. Buoy data is also helpful for validating our operational models. Note: The buoy previously stationed at M1 was relocated to M6 at the request of the Met Services. At the M1 station data collection was discontinued in 2007. Please note the weather buoys maybe intermittently inoperative during periods of servicing, or due to severe weather damage, vessel strikes or component failure. Any periods of in operation may</p>		
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						<p>result in gaps in the data record, depending on the nature of the failure. Real-time meteorological and oceanographic data collected from the Irish moored Weather Buoy network of stations. Parameters collected include: DateTime (yyyy-mm-ddThh:mm:ss.sss), Atmospheric Pressure (mbar), Air Temperature (degreeCelsius), DewPoint Temperature (degreeCelsius), Wind Speed (knots), Max Gust Wind Speed (knots), Wind Direction (degreeTrue), Sea Surface Temperature (degreeCelsius), Wave Period (seconds), Wave Height (metres) and Relative Humidity (%). Real-time data available for M2, M3, M4, M5 and M6. Historical data available for M1, FS1 and original M4 spatial location. Users of the download service can choose a station, time period, parameter(s) and output file type. Advanced download allows a user to define a bounding box area of</p>	
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						interest, selecting one or more buoys from the network. 'NaN' or '-999' describes missing or unavailable data.		
11	3.1	Sea Surface Temperature	daily_SST_Irish_Lights	Observations	https://erddap.irishlights.ie/erddap/tabledap/AllMetOcean.html?longitude%2Clatitude%2Ctime%2CLatlonName%2Cmmsi%2CAverageWindSpeed%2CGustSpeed%2CWindDirection%2CAirTemperature%2CRelativeHumidity%2CAirPressure%2CWaveHeight%2CWavePeriod%2CWaterTemperature&time%3E=2025-03-18T00%3A00%3A00Z	Daily SST - A selection of our lighthouses and buoys are equipped with meteorological and oceanographic (MetOcean) sensors and transmit their data to Irish Lights HQ. We currently have a number of buoys and lighthouses collecting weather and sea state data. Measurements include average wind speed, wind gust speed, average wind direction, gust direction, wave height, wave period and water temperature.		

12	3.1	Sea Surface Temperature	NOAA OISST	(satellites, ships, buoys and Argo floats)	Downloading and Preparing NOAA OISST Data · heatwaveR	<p>The OISST product is a global 1/4 degree gridded dataset of Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) derived SSTs at a daily resolution, starting on 1 September 1981. The source of the data is currently the NOAA NCDC. The NOAA 1/4° Daily Optimum Interpolation Sea Surface Temperature (OISST) is a long-term Climate Data Record that incorporates observations from different platforms (satellites, ships, buoys and Argo floats) into a regular global grid. The dataset is interpolated to fill gaps on the grid and create a spatially complete map of sea</p>	
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						surface temperature. Satellite and ship observations are referenced to buoys to compensate for platform differences and sensor biases.		
13	3.1	Sea Surface Temperature	Daily SST from locations around the Irish Coast - Malin Head, Wolfe Tone Bridge, Blennerville, Arklow Harbour	Observations	Office of Public Works	Presents instantaneous water level, flow and water temperature data graphically for the last week, month, year or complete record together with key thresholds and statistics, e.g., exceedance and significant flood data.		

14	3,2,4,5	SST,SSS, Subsurface temperature and salinity, Ocean currents,	Arctic Ocean Physics Reanalysis	Ranalysis	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/ARCTIC_MULTICYEAR_PHY_002_003/description	<p>The current version of the TOPAZ system - TOPAZ4b - is nearly identical to the real-time forecast system run at MET Norway. It uses a recent version of the Hybrid Coordinate Ocean Model (HYCOM) developed at University of Miami (Bleck 2002). HYCOM is coupled to a sea ice model; ice thermodynamics are described in Drange and Simonsen (1996) and the elastic-viscous-plastic rheology in Hunke and Dukowicz (1997). The model's native grid covers the Arctic and North Atlantic Oceans, has fairly homogeneous horizontal spacing (between 11 and 16 km). 50 hybrid layers are used in the vertical</p>	https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-0007
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						<p>(z-isopycnal). TOPAZ4b uses the Deterministic version of the Ensemble Kalman filter (DEnKF; Sakov and Oke 2008) to assimilate remotely sensed as well as temperature and salinity profiles. The output is interpolated onto standard grids and depths for convenience. Daily values are provided at all depths and surfaces momentum and heat fluxes are provided as well. Data assimilation, including the 100-member ensemble production, is performed weekly.</p>		
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WP4								
N	Task	Parameter/EOV/ECV	Dataset/Model Name	Type of Data	Link to Source	Brief description of the data	License	Citation (DOI/link to methodology paper or Best Practice)
1	4.6, 4.2, 4.3	Absolute dynamic topography, Sea Level Anomaly, and derived geostrophic currents	Global Ocean Gridded L 4 Sea Surface Heights And Derived Variables Reprocessed Copernicus Climate Service	Satellite	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/SEALEVEL_GLO_PHY_CLIMATE_L4_MY_008_057/description	DUACS delayed-time altimeter gridded maps of sea surface heights and derived variables over the global Ocean. This data set focuses on the stability and homogeneity of the sea level record by using stable two-satellite constellation. Available for the period 1 Jan 1993 to 7 Jun 2023 on a global 1/4° spatial grid resolution.		https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00145

2	4.6, 4.4, 4.2, 4.3	Absolute dynamic topography, Sea Level Anomaly, and derived geostrophic currents	Global Ocean Gridded L 4 Sea Surface Heights And Derived Variables Reprocessed 1993 Ongoing	Satellite	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/SEALEVEL_GLO_PHY_L4_MY_008_047/description	<p>Altimeter satellite gridded Sea Level Anomalies (SLA) computed with respect to a twenty-year [1993, 2012] mean. The SLA is estimated by Optimal Interpolation, merging the L3 along-track measurement from the different altimeter missions available. Available for the period 1 Jan 1993 to 7 Jun 2023 on a global 1/4° spatial grid resolution.</p>		https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00148
3	4.6,4.4	Absolute dynamic topography, Sea Level Anomaly, and derived geostrophic currents	European Seas Gridded L 4 Sea Surface Heights And Derived Variables Reprocessed 1993 Ongoing	Satellite	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/SEALEVEL_EUR_PHY_L4_MY_008_068/description	<p>Altimeter satellite gridded Sea Level Anomalies (SLA) computed with respect to a twenty-year [1993, 2012] mean. The SLA is estimated by Optimal Interpolation, merging the L3 along-track measurement from the</p>		https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00141

						different altimeter missions available. Available for the period 1 Jan 1993 to 7 Jun 2023 on a European Sea area 1/8° spatial grid resolution.	
4	4.6, 4.4	Absolute dynamic topography, Sea Level Anomaly, and derived geostrophic currents	European Seas Gridded L 4 Sea Surface Heights And Derived Variables Reprocessed Copernicus Climate Service	Satellite	https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/satellite-sea-level-mediterranean?tab=overview	DUACS delayed-time altimeter gridded maps of sea surface heights and derived variables over the global Ocean. This data set focuses on the stability and homogeneity of the sea level record by using stable two-satellite constellation. Available for the period 1 Jan 1993 to 3 Jun 2020 on a European Sea area 1/8° spatial grid resolution.	http://doi.org/10.24381/cds.012e84d8
5	4.5, 4.6, 4.4	Absolute dynamic topography, Sea Level Anomaly,	European Seas Along Track L 3 Sea Surface Heights Reprocessed 1993 Ongoing	Satellite	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/SEALEVEL_EUR_PHY_L3_MY_008_061/description	Altimeter satellite along-track sea surface heights anomalies (SLA) computed with respect to a twenty-year [1993, 2012]	https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00139

		and derived geostrophic currents				mean with a 1Hz (~7km) sampling.		
6	4.5, 4.6	Sea Surface Temperature	Global Ocean OSTIA Sea Surface Temperature and Sea Ice Reprocessed	Satellite	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/SST_GLO_ST_L4_REP_OBSERVATION_S_010_011/description	The OSTIA global sea surface temperature reprocessed product provides daily gap-free maps of foundation sea surface temperature and ice concentration at 0.05deg.x 0.05deg. horizontal grid resolution, using in-situ and satellite data. Period 1 Oct 1981 to 31 May 2022		https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00168
7	4.6	Sea Surface Temperature	Mediterranean Sea - High Resolution L4 Sea Surface Temperature Reprocessed	Satellite	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/SST_MED_ST_L4_REP_OBSERVATION_S_010_021/description	The Reprocessed Mediterranean dataset provides a stable and consistent long-term Sea Surface Temperature (SST) time series over the Mediterranean Sea developed for climate applications on a 0.05deg.x 0.05deg.		https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00173

						horizontal grid resolution. Period 3 Oct 1992 to 8 Jun 2023	
8	4.6	Sea Surface Salinity	SSS SMOS L4 OI - LOPS-v2021	Satellite-insitu	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/MULTIOBS_GLO_PHY_SSS_L4_MY_015_015/description	The product is obtained using optimal interpolation algorithm, that combine, ISAS in situ SSS OI analyses (Copernicus Marine Service products INSITU_GLO_PHY_TS_OA_NRT_013_002 and INSITU_GLO_PHY_TS_OA_MY_013_052) to reduce large scale and temporal variable bias and Soil Moisture Ocean Salinity (SMOS) satellite image with satellite SST information.	https://doi.org/10.1175/JTECH-D-20-0093.1
9	4.2, 4.3, 4.6	Chlorophyll-a	Copernicus-GlobColour	Satellite	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/OCEANCOLOUR_GLO_BGC_L4_MY_009_104/description	Chlorophyll-a from multiple satellite missions providing daily gap-free based on a space-time interpolation on a 4x4km	https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00281

						spatial resolution for the period 1 Sep 1997 to 31 Mar 2024		
10	4.2, 4.3, 4.5, 4.6	Absolute dynamic topography, Sea Level Anomaly, and derived geostrophic currents	SWOT Ocean Data Products	Satellite	https://www.aviso.altimetry.fr/en/missions/current-missions/swot/access-to-data.html	SWOT (Surface Water Ocean Topography) is a joint project including NASA, CNES, the Canadian Space Agency and the UK Space Agency. Provide sea surface heights (SSH) over a 120 km wide swath with a +/-10 km gap at the nadir track.		
11	4.2, 4.3, 4.5, 4.6	Temperature, ocean velocity, salinity, sea surface height	Global Ocean Physics Reanalysis	Model	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/GLOBAL_MULTYEAR_PHY_001_030/description	The GLORYS12V1 product is the CMEMS global ocean eddy-resolving (1/12° horizontal resolution, 50 vertical levels) reanalysis covering the altimetry (1993 onward).	https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00021	
12	4.2, 4.5, 4.6	Temperature, ocean velocity,	Mediterranean Sea Physics Reanalysis	Model	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/MEDSEA_MULTYEAR_PHY_006_004/description	The Med MFC physical multiyear product is a reanalysis product for the	https://doi.org/10.25423/CMCC/MEDSEA_MULTYEAR_PHY_006_004_E3R1	

		salinity, sea surface height			escription	mediterranean sea (1/24° horizontal resolution, 141 vertical levels) for the period 1 Jan 1987 to 1 Feb 2024.		
13	4.2	Temperature, ocean velocity, salinity, sea surface height	Western Mediterranean Operational forecasting system (WMOP)	Model	https://www.socib.es/?seccion=modelling&facility=forecast_system_description	WMOP is a high-resolution ocean forecasting system implemented over the Western Mediterranean Sea (~1/50° horizontal resolution, 32 vertical levels) developed at the Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System (SOCIB). Period 2014 onward.		http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/1755876X.2015.1117764
14	4.2	Temperature, ocean velocity, salinity	SOCIB Glider Missions - Canales Endurance Line	gliders	http://apps.socib.es/data-catalog/#/data-products/socib-canales-20230123-sdeep09-gfmr0142	SOCIB Glider Missions - Canales Endurance Line - cover the Ibiza channel since 2011. Ocean gliders provides temperature, salinity and ocean velocity from the surface to		

						seabed.		
15	4.2	Surface Currents	HF RADAR IBIZA	HF-radar	http://apps.socib.es/data-catalog/#/data-products/hf-radar-ibiza	Continuous hourly coastal ocean surface current maps in the Ibiza Channel measured by High-Frequency Radars since 2012		https://doi.org/10.25704/17gs-2b59
16	4.1	Near Surface Air temperature	MOSAIC	Weather station	https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.957760	This dataset contains information about the state of the central Arctic lower atmosphere during the Multidisciplinary drifting Observatory for the Study of Arctic Climate (MOSAIC) expedition. This dataset contains information about the state of the central Arctic lower atmosphere during the MOSAiC expedition. A 10-m meteorological tower provides near-surface temperature and temperature		https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.957760

						inversion characteristics		
17	4.1	Sea ice surface temperature	MOSAIc dataset collection	Ice mass balance buoys	https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.940692	Collection of datasets from SIMBA-type sea ice mass balance buoys deployed during the MOSAIc		https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.940692
18	4.1	Sea Ice Concentration	OSISAF dataset collection	Satellite	https://osi-saf.eumetsat.int/products/sea-ice-products	OSI-SAF Sea ice concentration (interim) climate data records, (i)CDRs, from SMMR/SSM/I/SSMIS and AMSR)		10.15770/EUM_SAF_OSI_0013
19	4.1	Sea ice surface temperature	C3S Sea Ice surface temperatures	Satellite	https://cds-test.copernicus-climate.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/satellite-sea-ice-temperature?tab=overview	Level 3 Sea ice surface temperature daily data from 1982 to 2019 derived from satellite observations from thermal Infrared satellite observations		Sea ice surface temperature daily data from 1982 to 2019 derived from satellite observations. Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS). DOI: 10.24381cdsxx.xxxxx
20	4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.6	Sea ice surface temperature	Copernicus-Marine-Service	Satellite	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/SEAICE_ARC_PHY_CLIMATE_L4_MY_011_016/description	Level 4 Arctic Sea and Ice surface temperature product based upon reprocessed AVHRR, (A)ATSR and SLSTR SST observations from the		https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00123

						ESA CCI project, the Copernicus C3S project and the AASTI dataset. The product is a daily interpolated field with a 0.05 degrees resolution, and covers surface temperatures in the ocean, the sea ice and the marginal ice zone.	
21	4.4	Temperature, Salinity	Copernicus-Marine-Service	In-situ observations, Satellite observations	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/MULTIOBS_GLO_PHY_TSUV_3D_MYNR_T_015_012/description	Multi Observation Global Ocean ARMOR3D L4 analysis and multi-year reprocessing data consisting of 3D Temperature, Salinity, Heights, Geostrophic Currents and Mixed Layer Depth, available on a 1/4 degree regular grid and on 50 depth levels from the surface down to the bottom.	DOI (product): https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00052
22	4.2	Temperature, Salinity,	Havstovan ocean data	In-situ observati	https://envofar.fo/data/index.php?dir=Timeseries&sort=	Dataset of calculated Faroe Bank Channel	https://doi.org/10.1029/2024-GL110

		subsurface ocean currents		ons	N&order=A	Overflow transport, temperature and salinity		097
23	4.2	subsurface ocean currents	Havstovan ocean data	In-situ observations	https://envofar.fo/data/index.php?dir=Currents%2FADCP_Data&sort=N&order=A	Processed and quality controlled ADCP data		https://doi.org/10.1029/2024-GL110097
24	4.2	Temperature, Salinity	Havstovan ocean data	In-situ observations	https://envofar.fo/data/index.php?dir=Hydrography&sort=N&order=A	Processed and quality controlled hydrographic		https://doi.org/10.1029/2024-GL110097
25	4.6, 4.4	Absolute dynamic topography, Sea Level Anomaly, and derived geostrophic currents	Sea level gridded data from satellite observations for the global ocean from 1993 to present	Satellite	https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/satellite-sea-level-global?tab=overview	Delayed-time altimeter gridded maps of sea surface heights and derived variables over the global Ocean. This data set focuses on the stability and homogeneity of the sea level record by using stable two-satellite constellation. Available for the period 1 Jan 1993 to 3 Jun 2020.		https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.4c328c78
26	4.3, 4.6	sea level along track data in Near real time	Global Ocean Along Track L3 Sea Surface Heights Nrt	Satellite		Quality see here: https://documentation.marine.copernicus.eu/QUID/CMEMS-SL-QUID-008-032		https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00147

						-068.pdf		
27		sea level along track data reprocessed	Global Ocean Along Track L3 Sea Surface Heights Reprocessed 1993 Ongoing Tailored For Data Assimilation	Satellite	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/SEALEVEL_GLO_PHY_L3_MY_008_062/description	Quality see here: https://documentation.marine.copernicus.eu/QUID/CMEMS-SL-QUID-008-032-068.pdf		https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00146
28	4.2	Continuous record of the full water column, trans-basin volume transports (Sv=106 m ³ /sec) in the subpolar North Atlantic (August 2014 - June 2020).	Meridional Overturning Circulation Observed by the Overturning in the Subpolar North Atlantic Program (OSNAP) Array from August 2014 to June 2020	data product from observations	OSNAP is consisted of about 60 moorings that stretch from Labrador to Greenland to Scotland, providing a continuous record of the full water column, trans-basin volume transports in the subpolar North Atlantic. The first 6 years of data (August 2014 - June 2020) from the full OSNAP array has been used to produce the monthly estimates of the MOC at OSNAP. All data are freely available	https://repository.gatech.edu/entities/publication/1744d4e2-0c93-44b2-af67-e76d3125af5b		https://doi.org/10.35090/gatech/70342

					from www.o-snap.org .			
29	4.2	5th generation reanalysis product ERA of the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF)	Atmospheric and surface ocean reanalysis	reanalysis data				https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.f17050d7
30	4.2, 4.3, 4.6	data product: NAO index (normalized)	station-based North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) index	observational data	Climatic Research Unit of the University of East Anglia	https://rmets.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/(SICI)1097-0088(19971115)17:13%3C1433::AID-JOC203%3E3.0.CO;2-P		https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-0088(19971115)17:13%3C1433::AID-JOC203%3E3.0.CO;2-P

WP5								
N	Task	Parameter/E OV/ECV	Dataset/Model Name	Type of Data	Link to Source	Brief description of the data	License	Citation (DOI/link to methodology paper or Best Practice)
1	5.2	Sea Surface Temperature and Salinity, Sea Surface Height	Multi-Model Large Ensemble Archive (MMLEA)	Model	https://www.cesm.ucar.edu/community-projects/mmlea	Global climate outputs from 18 models, 15 two-dimensional variables remapped to a common 2.5 x 2.5 degree grid.		Reference article DOI: https://doi.org/10.5194/esd-12-4-01-2021
2	5.2	Sea Surface Temperature	NOAA OI SST V2 High Resolution Dataset	Observational dataset	https://psl.noaa.gov/data/gribbed/data.noaa.oisst.v2.hghres.html	The NOAA Optimal Interpolation SST analysis provides global, spatially complete SSTs on a weekly and monthly basis for 1982-present.		
3	5.1	Subsurface temperature and salinity	EN4	Dataset collection	https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/hadobs/en4/	Quality-controlled subsurface ocean temperature and salinity profiles and objective analyses		

4	5.1	Arctic Sea ice volume	Global and regional ocean/sea ice reanalyses	ORA	https://psc.apl.uw.edu/research/projects/arctic-sea-ice-volume-anomaly/ https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_PHY_ENS_001_031/description	Monthly/daily variable on the original model grid	doi:10.1029/2011JC007084 doi:10.48670/moi-00024
5	5.1	Sea ice thickness	SEAICE_ARC_PHY_L4_NRT_011_014 from the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS)	Observational dataset	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/SEAICE_GLO_PHY_L4_NRT_011_014/description	Daily ice thickness and uncertainty estimation from measurements of CryoSat-2, Sentinel-3A, Sentinel-3B and Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity (SMOS)	doi:10.48670/moi-00125
6	5.1	Sea ice concentration	NOAA/NSIDC Climate Data Record version 5	Observational dataset	https://nsidc.org/data/g02202/versions/5	Daily and monthly time series of observed ice concentrations from 25 October 1978	doi: 10.7265/rjzb-pf78

7	5.1	Sea ice concentration	OSI-450-a	Observational dataset	https://osi-saf.eumetsat.int/products/osi-450-a	Daily average of observed fractional ice cover in percentage. Includes per-grid cell uncertainties.	doi:10.15770/EUM_SAF_OSI_0013
8	5.3	Sea Surface Temperature, Subsurface Temperature	CMIP6 Models SST models: CNRM-CM5 EC-Earth IPSL-CM5A-MR MPI-ESM-MR CMCC-CM MPI-ESM-LR EC-Earth3-Veg CNRM-ESM2-1	Model	https://esgf-node.ipsl.upmc.fr/search/cmip6-ipsl/	Climate model outputs for historical and future projection	Eyring et al. (2016) https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-9-1937-2016

9	5.3	Sea Surface Temperature, Subsurface Temperature	<p>Med-CORDEX</p> <p>SST outputs from: CNRM-RCSM4 CLMcom-GUF-CCLM5-0-9-NEMOMED12-3-6 LMD-LMDZMED_v2 CMCC-CCLM-21-NEMO MFS UBEL-EBUPOM2c AWI-GERICS-ROM22 CNRM-RCSM6</p> <p>Subsurface temperature outputs from: CNRM-RCSM4 CLMcom-GUF-CCLM5-0-9-NEMOMED12-3-6 CMCC-CCLM-21-NEMO MFS CNRM-RCSM6</p>	Model	<p>https://www.medcordex.eu/ Daily model outputs have been requested to the developers</p>	Regional Climate System Models outputs for historical and future projections		<p>Ruti et al. (2016) https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-14-00176.1</p>
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10	5.3	Sea Level	<p><i>CMIP6 Models:</i> NorESM2-MM MPI-ESM1-2-HR GFDL-ESM4 CMCC-ESM2 NorESM2-LM MIROC6 FGOALS-g3 CMCC-CM2-SR5 NESM3 KIOST-ESM EC-Earth3-Veg-LR BCC-CSM2-MR MRI-ESM2-0 IPSL-CM6A-LR EC-Earth3-Veg ACCESS-ESM1-5 MPI-ESM1-2-LR INM-CM5-0 EC-Earth3 ACCESS-CM2</p>	Model	<p>https://esgf-index1.ceda.ac.uk/search/cmip6-ceda/</p>	Climate model outputs for historical and future projection		
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11	5.3	Sea Ice	CMIP6 Models: AWI-ESM-1-1-LR/MR CanESM5 CNRM-ESM2-1 CNRM-CM6-1 MPI-ESM-1-2-HAM IPSL-CM6A-LR MIROC6 UKESM1-0-LL MPI-ESM1-2-LR GISS-E2-1-G CESM2 NorESM2-LM/MM GFDL-CM4 NESM3	Model	https://esgf-node.ipsl.upmc.fr/search/cmip6-ipsl/	Climate model outputs for historical and future projection		
12	5.4	Sea-ice EO/ECV time series	CMIP6 Models	Model	https://doi.org/10.22033/ESGF/CMIP6.10843	Calibrated climate model with sea ice EO/ECV		
13	5.1, 5.3	Sea-ice EO/ECV time series	CMIP6: NorESM, CMCC-CM2, IITM-ESM, ECMWF-IFS	Model	https://aims2.llnl.gov/search	Climate model outputs for historical and future projection		
14	5.1	sea-ice EO/ECV time series	Destination Earth simulations	Model	https://destination-earth.eu/destination-earth/destination-components/destination	High-resolution global climate model outputs for historical and near-future		https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2405880723000559

					n-earth-data-lake/	projections		
15	5.3	Sea Surface Temperature, Subsurface Temperature	Destination Earth simulations	Model	https://destination-earth.eu/destination-earth/destination-components/destination-earth-data-lake/	High-resolution global climate model outputs for historical and near-future projections		https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2405880723000559
16	5.4	ECV Nutrient (Silicate, phosphate, nitrate), Ocean Inorganic Carbon (TA, DIC, pCO2), Subsurface Temperature and Subsurface Salinity	NorCPM1	Model	https://doi.org/10.11582/2025.00004 https://doi.org/10.22033/ESGF/CMIP6.10843 https://doi.org/10.11582/2024.00001	Model simulation data from the experiments NorESM_PP, REANA_DP, REANA_PP, REANA_GP, REANA_SP and REANA_GP2 are available on the first link. The remaining experiments, NorESM_DP and REANA_IAV_GP2, are available on link 2 and 3 respectively.		https://doi.org/10.1029/2024MS004237

WP6								
N	Task	Parameter/EOV/ECV	Dataset/Model Name	Type of Data	Link to Source	Brief description of the data	License	Citation (DOI/link to methodology paper or Best Practice)
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WP7								
N	Task	Parameter/EOV/ECV	Dataset/Model Name	Type of Data	Link to Source	Brief description of the data	License	Citation (DOI/link to methodology paper or Best Practice)
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Table 4 - Data Inventory.

Annex 2: Minimum set of metadata for in situ data

Variable name	Attribute name	Data type	Description	Mandatory	Notes
NC_GLOBAL	acknowledgement	string	A place to acknowledge various types of support for the project that produced this data		https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000373775
NC_GLOBAL	cdm_data_type	string	Data type according to Common Data Model (possible values: Grid, MovingGrid, Other, Point, Profile, RadialSweep, TimeSeries, TimeSeriesProfile, Swath, Trajectory, TrajectoryProfile)	yes	https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/data/oceans/ncei/formats/netcdf/v2.0/index.html
NC_GLOBAL	contributors_name	string	The name of any individuals, projects, or institutions that contributed to the creation of this data. May be presented as free text, or in a structured format compatible with conversion to ncML (e.g., insensitive to changes in whitespace, including end-of-line characters)		It should include the principal investigator (coordinator of the data collection). The PI guarantees that the list is complete and that other authors have agreed to publish their names

NC_GLOBAL	contributors_orcid	string	ORCID of any individuals or institutions that contributed to the collection of this data (separated by comma)		It should include the principal investigator (coordinator of the data collection). The PI guarantees that the list is complete and that other authors have agreed to publish their orcid
NC_GLOBAL	contributors_role	string	The role of any individuals, projects, or institutions that contributed to the creation of this data. May be presented as free text, or in a structured format compatible with conversion to ncML (e.g., insensitive to changes in whitespace, including end-of-line characters). Multiple roles should be presented in the same order and number as the names in contributor_names		It should include the principal investigator (coordinator of the data collection). The PI guarantees that the list is complete and that other authors have agreed to publish their role
NC_GLOBAL	Conventions	string	Conventions used to define dataset metadata	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	creator_name	string	The name of the person (or other creator type specified by the creator_type attribute) principally responsible for creating this data	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	creator_type	string	Specifies type of creator with one of the following: 'person', 'group', 'institution', or 'position'. If this attribute is not specified, the creator is assumed to be a person	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	creator_url	string	The URL of the person (or other creator type	yes	

			specified by the creator_type attribute) principally responsible for creating this data		
NC_GLOBAL	data_best_practices_doi	string	Data best practices DOI	yes, if existing	
NC_GLOBAL	data_creation	string	Date of dataset creation	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	data_dataset	string	URL to ERDDAP data dataset (in case of collection for which there are 2 different dataset for data and metadata) - connected to metadata: metadata_dataset		
NC_GLOBAL	data_doi	string	Data DOI	yes, if existing	
NC_GLOBAL	data_format_original	string	Original format of the dataset	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	data_update	string	Date of dataset update	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	data_update_frequence	string	Frequence of dataset update	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	data_version	string	Dataset update version	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	distributor_name	string	Name of the entity from which we are federating information		
NC_GLOBAL	distributor_url	string	URL of the entity from which we are federating information		
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_lat_max	double	Max latitude expressed in WGS84 (the highest possible precision)	yes, if spatial data	
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_lat_min	double	Min latitude expressed in WGS84 (the highest	yes, if spatial	

			possible precision)	data	
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_lat_resolution	double	Latitude resolution expressed in WGS84 (for grid data)	yes, if spatial grid data	
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_lat_units	string	Degrees north	yes, if spatial data	
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_lon_max	double	Max longitude expressed in WGS84 (the highest possible precision)	yes, if spatial data	
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_lon_min	double	Min longitude expressed in WGS84 (the highest possible precision)	yes, if spatial data	
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_lon_resolution	double	Longitude resolution expressed in WGS84 (for grid data)	yes, if spatial grid data	
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_lon_units	string	Degrees east	yes, if spatial data	
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_vertical_max	double	Max vertical extension (in case of vertical profile) (the highest possible precision)	yes, if spatial data	
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_vertical_min	double	Min vertical extension (in case of vertical profile) (the highest possible precision)	yes, if spatial data	
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_vertical_positive	string	Positive direction of vertical extension ("up" means that z increases up - height, "down" means that z increases downward - pressure or depth)	yes, if spatial data	
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_vertical_units	string	Units used for the vertical extension	yes, if spatial	

				data	
NC_GLOBAL	infoUrl	string	URL of data information background (es. GeoNetwork, project web page, dataset page, ...)	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	inspire	string	INSPIRE spatial data or SeaDataNet vocabulary	yes, if spatial data	
NC_GLOBAL	institution	string	The name of the institution principally responsible for originating this data. This attribute is recommended by the CF convention	yes	Owner
NC_GLOBAL	institution_edmo_code	string	EDMO code of the institution principally responsible for this data (owner or provider)	yes	See specific project list on EDMERP SeaDataNet
NC_GLOBAL	institution_edmo_uri	string	EDMO URI of the institution principally responsible for this data (owner or provider)	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	institution_ror_code	string	ROR code of the institution principally responsible for this data (owner or provider)	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	institution_ror_uri	string	ROR URI of the institution principally responsible for this data (owner or provider)	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	keywords	string	List of keywords and phrases (separated by comma - in case of multiple vocabularies, insert keywords following the same order listed in "keywords_vocabulary")	yes	

NC_GLOBAL	keywords_vocabulary	string	Identifies the controlled list of keywords from which the values in the "keywords" attribute are taken (in case of multiple vocabularies, separated by comma)	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	license	string	Licence that describes the restrictions to data access and distribution (CC-BY)	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	license_url	string	Link to license url	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	metadata_dataset	string	URL to ERDDAP metadata dataset (in case of collection for which there are 2 different dataset for data and metadata) - connected to metadata: data_dataset		
NC_GLOBAL	metadata_source	string	URL to data source metadata		
NC_GLOBAL	naming_authority	string	Name of who defines the data set and the standards to be applied	yes	Fixed value
NC_GLOBAL	oceanographic_campaign	string	Name of the oceanographic campaign during which the data were collected		
NC_GLOBAL	platform_id_orig	string	Pre-existing platform id, if applicable		
NC_GLOBAL	platform_type_sdn_name	string	Name of the platform type according to SeaDataNet vocabulary		
NC_GLOBAL	platform_type_sdn_uri	string	URI of the platform type according to SeaDataNet vocabulary		

NC_GLOBAL	platform_type_sdn_urn	string	URN of the platform type according to SeaDataNet vocabulary		
NC_GLOBAL	platform_wmo	double	Platform identification numbers according to World Meteorological Organization		
NC_GLOBAL	project_code	string	Project code/acronym	yes	ObsSea4Clim
NC_GLOBAL	Project_DOI	string	Project DOI	yes	https://doi.org/10.3030/101136548
NC_GLOBAL	project_edmerp	string	Project EDMERP code	yes	13765
NC_GLOBAL	project_edmerp_uri	string	Project EDMERP uri	yes	https://edmerp.seadatanet.org/report/13765
NC_GLOBAL	project_id	double	Project Grant agreement number	yes	101136548
NC_GLOBAL	project_name	string	Project name	yes	Ocean observations and indicators for climate and assessments
NC_GLOBAL	project_statement	string	Project Grant agreement statement	yes	Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

NC_GLOBAL	publisher_name	string	The name of the person (or other entity specified by the publisher_type attribute) responsible for publishing the data file or product to users, with its current metadata and format.		
NC_GLOBAL	publisher_type	string	Specifies type of publisher with one of the following: 'person', 'group', 'institution', or 'position'. If this attribute is not specified, the publisher is assumed to be a person.		
NC_GLOBAL	publisher_url	string	The URL of the person (or other entity specified by the publisher_type attribute) responsible for publishing the data file or product to users, with its current metadata and format.		
NC_GLOBAL	references	string	Description of how the dataset was created: published or web-based references that describe the data or methods used to produce it. Recommend URIs (such as a URL or DOI) for papers or other references. This attribute is defined in the CF conventions.	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	ship_call_sign	string	Maritime call sign assigned as unique alphanumeric identifier to the ship		
NC_GLOBAL	ship_imo	double	IMO ship identification number (unique ship identifier) - report only the seven-digit number		

NC_GLOBAL	ship_name	string	Name of the ship		https://vocab.ices.dk/?ref=315
NC_GLOBAL	source	string	The method of collection and production of the dataset (e.g., types of instrument, model, collection). If it was model-generated, source should name the model and its version. If it is observational, source should characterize it. This attribute is defined in the CF Conventions	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	standard_name_vocabulary	string	Name and version of standard vocabulary (e.g., CF Standard Name Table v70)	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	summary	string	A paragraph describing the dataset, analogous to an abstract for a paper	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	time_coverage_duration	string	Time coverage duration using ISO 8601 (in alternative to time_coverage_start/time_coverage_end)	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	time_coverage_end	string	Time coverage end using ISO 8601	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	time_coverage_resolution	string	Time coverage resolution using ISO 8601 (if applicable)	yes, if applicable	
NC_GLOBAL	time_coverage_start	string	Time coverage start using ISO 8601	yes	

NC_GLOBAL	title	string	A short phrase or sentence describing the dataset. In many discovery systems, the title will be displayed in the results list from a search, and therefore should be human readable and reasonable to display in a list of such names	yes	
variable	ecv	string	Essential Climate Variable (ECV): physical, chemical or biological variable or a group of linked variables that critically contributes to the characterization of Earth's climate	yes, if applicable	Generally use ECV, alternatively for the ocean use EOVS (which are included in ECV). The important thing is to be consistent between ecv and ecv_uri
			Essential Ocean Variable (EOV): physical, biochemical or biological variable or a group of linked variables that help to deliver ocean forecasts and early warnings, climate projections and assessments and protect ocean health and its benefits	yes, if applicable	
variable	ecv_uri	string	URI to the Essential Climate Variable (ECV)	yes, if applicable	Generally use ECV, alternatively for the ocean use EOVS (which are included in ECV). The important thing is to be consistent between ecv and ecv_uri
			URI to the Essential Ocean Variable (EOV)	yes, if applicable	

variable	standard_name	string	A long descriptive name for the variable taken from a controlled vocabulary of variable names. We recommend using the CF convention and the variable names from the CF standard name table. This attribute is recommended by the CF convention.	yes	https://erddap.ifremer.fr/erddap/info/ArgoFloats/index.html
variable	long_name	string	Long name of the variable	yes	https://erddap.ifremer.fr/erddap/info/ArgoFloats/index.html
variable	parameter_sdn_name	string	Name of the parameter according to SeaDataNet vocabulary	yes	
variable	parameter_sdn_uri	string	URI of the parameter according to SeaDataNet vocabulary	yes	
variable	parameter_sdn_urn	string	URN of the parameter according to SeaDataNet vocabulary	yes	
variable	unit_sdn_name	string	Name of the unit of measurement according to SeaDataNet vocabulary	yes	
variable	unit_sdn_uri	string	URI of the unit of measurement according to SeaDataNet vocabulary	yes	
variable	unit_sdn_urn	string	URN of the unit of measurement according to SeaDataNet vocabulary	yes	
variable	units	string	Unit of measurement of the variable needed by ERDDAP	yes	

variable	units_url	string	URL to the vocabulary used to define the unit of measurement of the variable in "units"	yes	
variable	variable_best_practices_doi	string	Variable best practices DOI (if the same of the data insert the same value of "data_best_practice_doi")	yes, if existing	
variable	sensor_manufacturer_sdn_name	string	Name of the sensor manufacturer or developer according to SeaDataNet vocabulary	yes, if applicable	
variable	sensor_manufacturer_sdn_uri	string	URI of the sensor manufacturer or developer according to SeaDataNet vocabulary	yes, if applicable	
variable	sensor_manufacturer_sdn_urn	string	URN of the sensor manufacturer or developer according to SeaDataNet vocabulary	yes, if applicable	
variable	sensor_sdn_name	string	Name of the sensor according to SeaDataNet vocabulary	yes, if applicable	
variable	sensor_sdn_uri	string	URI of the sensor according to SeaDataNet vocabulary	yes, if applicable	
variable	sensor_sdn_urn	string	URN of the sensor according to SeaDataNet vocabulary	yes, if applicable	
variable	sensor_last_calibration	string	Date of the last calibration of the sensor	yes, if applicable	
variable	sensor_accuracy	string	Accuracy of the sensor	yes, if applicable	

variable	sensor_uncertainty	string	Value of uncertainty of the sensor	yes, if applicable	
variable	sensor_uncertainty_url	string	External link to the methodology used to calculate the value of uncertainty of the sensor (e.g., DOI, URL)	yes, if applicable	
variable	standard_name	string	Fixed standard name for quality check "quality_flag"	yes	
variable	long_name	string	Long name of the variable	yes	https://erddap.ifremer.fr/erddap/info/ArgoFloats/index.html
variable	flag_meanings	string	One or more values separated by comma that indicate the meaning of the QC flags of the variable, there must be a match with the one entered in "flag_values" (possible value: no_qc_performed, good_data, probably_good_data, bad_data_that_are_potentially_correctable, bad_data, value_changed, not_used, nominal_value, interpolated_value, missing_value)	yes	
variable	flag_values	string	One or more values separated by comma that indicate the QC flags of the variable, there must be a match with the one entered in "flag_meanings" (possible values: 0,1,2,3,4,5,7,8,9)	yes	

variable	qc_manual	string	Quality Flag Scheme	yes, if applicable	
variable	qc_method	string	Quality Flag Method (DOI or other reference)	yes, if applicable	

Table 5: Metadata.

Annex 3: Zenodo Guide

The following Figures are a visual representation of the action to be taken on ObsSea4Clim Zenodo repository.

1. ObsSea4Clim dedicated Zenodo repository page can be accessed at the link: <https://zenodo.org/communities/obssea4clim/>
2. To upload the desired item, click on the upper right-hand *New upload* (Fig.3).

Fig. 3: ObsSea4Clim Zenodo Community - New upload.

3. On the upload page, you can add an existing DOI by selecting "Yes" and entering the URL, or select "No" to have a DOI automatically assigned by Zenodo to the uploaded item (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4: ObsSea4Clim Zenodo Community - DOI.

4. If the community is not selected, click on the blue button on top *Search a community* (Fig.5).

Fig. 5: ObsSea4Clim Zenodo Community - Search Community.

5. In the search bar of the new page, write *ObsSea4Clim* and then select the community (Fig.6).

Fig. 6: ObsSea4Clim Zenodo Community - Select a Community.

6. It is also important to tag the *Awards/Grants* in the Founding section . Click on Add [1], insert the *Grant Number (101136548)* [2], select the ObsSea4Clim. project and then click on the Add button on the bottom right [3] (Fig.7).

The screenshot shows the 'Funding' section of the Zenodo interface. At the top, there is a blue bar with the text 'Funding' and a right-pointing arrow. Below this, the 'Awards/Grants' section is visible, containing two buttons: '+ Add' and '+ Add custom'. A red arrow labeled '1' points to the '+ Add' button.

Below the buttons is a form titled 'Add standard award/grant'. It features a search input field containing '101136548', a search icon, and a 'Funder' dropdown menu. Below the search field is a list of search results, each with a radio button and a title. A red arrow labeled '2' points to the first result: 'Mitigating Energy Poverty through Innovative Solutions' by the Latvian Council of Science.

Below the list is a pagination bar with numbers 1 through 5, and an 'Add' button. A red arrow labeled '3' points to the 'ObsSea4Clim — Ocean observations and indicators for climate and assessments.' project in the search results.

At the bottom of the form is a 'Cancel' button and a blue 'Add' button. A red arrow labeled '4' points to the 'Add' button.

Fig. 7: ObsSea4Clim Zenodo Community - Founding Section.